

Replication README:

Robot Adoption and Occupational Health

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Overview

This document provides details for replicating the analysis in the paper *Robot Adoption and Occupational Health* by Filomena M. and Principe, F. The study investigates the impact of industrial robot adoption on occupational health outcomes in Italian provinces between 2008 and 2018.

Data Sources

This project uses several datasets.

The first is provided by the **International Federation of Robotics (IFR)**, offering data on annual robot shipments by industry. These data are mapped to the provincial level using employment shares. Access to IFR data typically requires a subscription or institutional access. More information on are to aquire the data can be found at the following link: <https://ifr.org/worldrobotics/>.

The second dataset comes from **INAIL**, the Italian Workers' Compensation Authority. It includes annual data on workplace injuries by province and sector for the years 2008–2018. These data can be accessed via INAIL's statistical portal or requested from the agency. The data are aggregated at the provincial level and merged with the IFR-derived measures of robot adoption.

To map robot exposure to provinces, we use historical sectoral employment shares as weights. These are computed using data from the **Italian Population Census** (Censimento Generale dell'Industria e dei Servizi), provided by **ISTAT**, for the years 1981, 1991, and 2001. These data were originally accessible through ISTAT's online data portals or through microdata requests, although public availability may have changed over time. These sectoral shares are used both to construct the treatment intensity (robot exposure) and to develop instrumental variables, following the standard approach in the literature.

Current sector-level employment data at the provincial level, used as the denominator in the construction of injury rates and other outcomes, are also obtained from **ISTAT**. These data were previously available via ISTAT's "Struttura e dimensione delle unità locali delle imprese"

or similar labor market statistics portals. Access may now require direct requests or restricted-use data.

To examine mechanisms and heterogeneous effects, we additionally rely on microdata from the **Labour Force Survey (LFS)** conducted by ISTAT. These data provide detailed information on worker characteristics, sectoral and occupational distribution, and employment conditions at the province-year level, which are used to explore channels of adjustment in response to automation. These data are available upon request and upon submission of a research proposal through the ISTAT microdata portal: <https://www.istat.it/dati/microdati/>.

Finally, data on **occupational physical intensity (OPI)** are used in the construction of task-based heterogeneity measures. These measures follow the methodology developed by Khron (2020) and related work, and are matched to Italian occupational codes. Since OPI data are not the main focus of the analysis, we mention their construction and origin in the main text, referring to the source study.

Further details on data construction, sources, and variable definitions are provided in the Data section and in Table A.1 of the Appendix. Scripts used in the analysis are also made available.

Contact

For questions related to the replication files or methodology, please contact the authors:

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We welcome feedback and are happy to assist with replication efforts or related research inquiries.